

State-of-the-Art Advances in Structural Control of Buildings: Methods and Algorithms for Active Control of Seismic Response

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Abstract

This state-of-the-art review presents an overview of structural control strategies for mitigating the seismic response of buildings, including passive, semi-active, active, and hybrid systems, with reference to real-world implementations. Emphasis is placed on active control, which allows real-time adaptation of control forces based on structural response, enhancing resilience during seismic events. The review discusses numerical modeling of multi-degree-of-freedom structures, with equations of motion formulated in state-space form to support implementation of control algorithms.

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1.1 Systems for Structural Control (Passive, Semi-Active, Active, Hybrid)

Structural control is a topic of great interest for both the community of civil engineers and automation engineers. The intense concern manifested over the years is fueled by the need to achieve safer constructions that remain operational after the occurrence of extreme events. Although the development of constructions has been a principal element in society throughout history, the accelerated vertical expansion of cities in recent decades generates continuous challenges in this field. Current approaches in the design of structural systems assume that constructions are designed to ensure uninterrupted functioning only in the event of extreme phenomena with a short return period. In the case of more destructive events, with a longer return period, the primary objective is the safety of the occupants, even at the expense of functional and structural integrity. In other words, extensive controlled but damage of structural and non-structural elements is accepted, leading to the temporary decommissioning of the building.

More precisely, the energy generated by tectonic movement is transmitted through the foundation to the structural system of the building. This energy is absorbed by the structural elements in the form of kinetic energy, damping energy, and elastic and inelastic (hysteretic) deformation energy. To illustrate this energy exchange, [1] presents the subject in analogy with the process of rainwater collection by a building's drainage system.

Figure 1.1: Analogy regarding the distribution of seismic energy (adapted after [1])

In Figure 1.1, the analogy illustrating the distribution of seismic energy during an earthquake can be visualized. The collected rainwater represents the input seismic energy transmitted to the structural system. Initially, this energy is transformed into kinetic energy, generated by the

mass of the structure mobilizing inertial forces. As the structure begins to vibrate, the structural elements deform and absorb energy. At the moment the structure stops, at maximum displacement, all kinetic energy is transformed into deformation energy. This process is illustrated in Figure 1.1 by a pump connecting the lower and upper parts of the containers representing kinetic energy and elastic deformation energy. Thus, the vibration of the structure can be visualized as a continuous transformation of kinetic energy into deformation energy and vice versa. Furthermore, it can also be observed that as this exchange occurs, some of the energy is lost, transforming into damping energy. This triple energy exchange characterizes systems with elastic response. In this case, the transfer between kinetic energy and deformation energy occurs until all incoming seismic energy equals the damping energy.

On the other hand, if the deformation energy exceeds a certain limit, it permanently transforms into hysteretic energy. This limit is determined by the elastic deformations capable of the structural elements, beyond which non-linear behavior begins to manifest through damage to the constructive elements of the building. In this case, at the end of the seismic movement, the incoming seismic energy will equal the sum of the energy dissipated through damping and the hysteretic energy dissipated through inelastic deformations.

In this context, the implementation of structural control aims to minimize the total amount of hysteretic energy dissipated through inelastic deformations, utilizing systems for structural control. Depending on how they operate, systems for structural control are divided into:

- **Passive control systems;**
- **Active control systems;**
- **Semi-active control systems;**
- **Hybrid control systems;**

1.1.1 Passive Control Systems

Passive systems encompass equipment attached to the structural framework that serves to dissipate/isolate part of the energy induced by seismic movement. They operate without their own energy source, and their behavior characteristics remain constant during the dynamic response of the structure. Thus, this type of system does not have the capacity to adapt its characteristics based on the global seismic response of the structural framework, but can be designed to have an optimal effect only under specific conditions, depending on the vibration characteristics of the building. As proposed by [2], passive control systems can be divided into two major categories: *seismic isolation systems* and *dissipative systems*.

Seismic Isolation Systems

Seismic isolation involves the introduction of a system with high vertical stiffness at the base, having significantly greater horizontal flexibility than that of the building. Thus, the isolator system aims to limit the seismic energy reaching the structural framework. The main objective is to change the natural vibration characteristics of the building by introducing a new predominant mode of vibration with a much longer period, to keep the structure away from the frequency content of the seismic excitation. Seismic isolation systems consist of two main subsystems [1]:

- Isolation system, composed of flexible elements that ensure the "decoupling" of the structure from the foundation ground and that modify the natural vibration characteristics of the building. These can include: natural rubber elastomeric isolators (*Natural Rubber Bearing - NRB*), high damping elastomeric isolators made of synthetic rubber (*High*

Damping Rubber Bearings - HDRB), lead-core rubber isolators (Lead Rubber Bearings - LRB), sliding bearings (Sliding Bearings - SB)

Figure 1.2: Seismic isolators: a) ¹ seismic isolator concept - LRB b) ² seismic isolator in operation

- Damping system, which primarily serves to dissipate part of the seismic energy absorbed by the structural system, to prevent excessive rigid body displacements. Additionally, it is also used to return the building to its initial position when the deformation of the isolators is equal to zero.

Figure 1.3: Seismic isolation system composed of isolators and dampers ³

As highlighted in Figure 1.4, the isolation system modifies how the building responds to seismic excitations. The high flexibility of the isolators, coupled with the high stiffness of the structural framework, leads to the building moving as a whole (rigid body displacement). In this way, it avoids the occurrence of significant relative level displacements that can lead to excessive damage of structural and non-structural elements.

The implementation of this type of system is effective only for structures with high and medium natural frequencies, for which vibration is transmitted through the foundation ground.

¹source: <https://www.boomarine.com/products/lead-rubber-bearing>, (accessed on 28.01.2023)

²source: <https://civildigital.com/base-isolation-system-outline-on-principles-types-advan> (accessed on 28.01.2023)

³source: <https://www.fujiengineering.com/yimg/r37.jpg> (accessed on 28.01.2023)

Figure 1.4: Structural response: a) without seismic isolation system b) with seismic isolation system

For buildings sensitive to wind action or other direct actions, the use of this type of system is not feasible [3].

Dissipative Systems

Dissipative systems consist of equipment installed in the superstructure of buildings, operating without an energy source or external automatic control, and are designed to absorb part of the seismic energy taken by the structural system. These systems are most commonly used to reduce structural response, both in new buildings and for improving the seismic performance of existing buildings. To contribute effectively to the structural response, dissipative equipment must be judiciously placed within the structure. Moreover, they must be calibrated so that the dissipative effect is mobilized under specific circumstances. Depending on how their action is engaged, dissipative systems are divided into [1]: *displacement-activated systems*, *velocity-activated systems*, and *motion-activated systems*.

- Displacement-activated systems dissipate the seismic energy taken by the structural system based on the relative displacements occurring between the connection points of the dissipative equipment. They come into play proportionally with the development of internal forces in the structural elements and serve to consume part of the elastic deformation energy induced by the earthquake. Some of the most common such devices include: *metal hysteretic dampers* - represented by highly ductile metal parts that dissipate energy through cyclic inelastic deformations; *friction dampers* - made of an assembly composed of metal pieces joined with high-strength bolts that dissipate energy when the friction force is exceeded, allowing them to move relative to each other.

Also included in this category are *self-centering dampers*, which, in addition to their dissipative component, have the ability to return to the initial state after the load has ceased, thus minimizing any residual deformations that may occur at the level of the structural elements (Figure 1.6 b)).

- Velocity-activated systems dissipate the seismic energy taken by the structural system based on the relative velocities recorded between the connection points of the dissipative equipment, with maximum damping forces being generated out of phase with the moment when the maximum efforts are recorded at the level of the structural elements. Thus, they

⁴photo source: https://www.technoarete.org/common_abstract/pdf/IJERMCE/v5/i1/Ext_08356.pdf (accessed on 09.02.2023)

⁵photo source: <https://www.damptech.com/> (accessed on 09.02.2023)

Figure 1.5: Displacement-activated systems: a) ⁴hysteretic metal damper b) ⁵friction damper

Figure 1.6: a) Hysteretic behavior: a) hysteretic metal damper [4] b) self-centering damper [5]

serve to supplement the energy dissipated by the structural system. Velocity-activated systems generally consist of *viscous dampers* or *viscoelastic dampers*.

Viscous dampers Figure 1.7 are mechanical systems that dissipate energy by deforming a fluid with high viscosity. These devices generally consist of a steel cylinder inside which hydraulic or silicone fluid is subjected to pressure generated by the movement of a piston whose head has passage orifices. They may also have a reaction chamber designed to suppress the general elastic reaction to the pressure applied to the fluid [6]. These systems are not sensitive to temperature; however, they have a shortcoming in their ability to engage early in the structural response due to the fact that the magnitude of the damping force is proportional to the velocity at which the piston moves.

Viscoelastic dampers Figure 1.8 are made using materials with viscoelastic properties that dissipate energy through shear deformations. During deformation, the viscoelastic material behaves both as a viscous liquid and as an elastic solid, having the ability to return to its original shape after unloading. The performance of this type of equipment

⁶photo source: <https://structurae.net/en/products-services/dampers-for-butterfly-towers-of-bucharest> (accessed on 11.02.2023)

Figure 1.7: Viscous damper: a) viscous damper concept b) ⁶viscous dampers implemented at Orhidea Towers, Bucharest

is influenced by temperature and loading frequency. The first buildings equipped with such systems were the World Trade Center towers in New York, which served to reduce acceleration levels to ensure occupant comfort during wind actions [6].

Figure 1.8: Viscoelastic damper: a) viscoelastic damper concept b) viscoelastic damper proposed by [7]

- Motion-activated systems do not directly dissipate seismic energy but rather absorb some of it from the building through control equipment. In this case, the kinetic energy at the level of the structural system becomes input energy for the passive system, which in turn absorbs it in the form of kinetic energy, damping energy, and elastic deformation.

In general, these systems consist of a mass (1%-2% of the building's mass) that is attached to the structural system so that its dynamic characteristics are tuned to those of the building's fundamental vibration mode. Thus, during motion, the system is in resonance with the building, generating inertial forces in the opposite direction to the direction of its displacement. In practice, two such systems are encountered: *tuned mass dampers (TMD)* and *tuned liquid dampers (TLD)*.

Compared to tuned mass dampers, tuned liquid dampers are much simpler, generating lower maintenance costs, are easier to install, and can be easily used to control motion in both directions. Additionally, the much lower friction forces ensure efficiency even for low-frequency and low-amplitude vibrations. However, considering that in the case of

⁷Photo source: http://www.tesolution.com/uploads/6/9/3/0/69304001/dsc07463_orig.jpg (accessed on 12.02.2023)

Figure 1.9: Concept of motion-activated systems

Figure 1.10: a) ⁷tuned mass damper b) tuned liquid damper [8]

TMD the mass is generally made of steel, a TLD requires a much larger volume of liquid to generate the same inertial force.

1.1.2 Active Control Systems

Despite their high reliability and relatively low implementation costs, passive systems have limited effectiveness in reducing structural response. For example, base isolation systems are not effective in the case of direct actions on buildings, while dissipative systems can only dissipate energy from a single mode of vibration. These systems do not have the capacity to adapt to the type of dynamic loading acting on the building or to changes in dynamic characteristics that may occur when the structural system behaves inelastically. Once installed, a passive system will behave in a predefined manner, regardless of the global response of the building.

Considering these limitations, the implementation of active control systems naturally emerges as a solution that offers the possibility of monitoring the behavior of the construc-

tion, with the capability to make decisions and act in real time to ensure a favorable response of the structure. An active control system encompasses three subsystems:

- **Monitoring system** - its role is to measure seismic excitation and the structural response manifested in specific areas in the form of accelerations, velocities, or displacements, using sensors or other measuring equipment.
- **Control system** - aggregates and filters information from sensors, using it within a control algorithm to calculate an appropriate response method from the actuation system.
- **Actuation system** - consists of execution elements that receive and implement the command calculated by the control system.

Figure 1.11: Building - active control system interaction [9]

As shown in Figure 1.11, the active control system can be seen as equipment within the building, which monitors structural response and applies control forces based on a numerical algorithm.

The main active control systems encountered in the specialized literature are: *Active tendon systems (ATS)*, *Active bracing systems (ABS)*, *Active mass dampers (AMD)*

- **Active tendon systems** - are generally made from a set of tendons connected to the building structure, whose tensioning is controlled through an electro-hydraulic actuation mechanism governed by a control algorithm. The advantage of this system is that it can be easily implemented in constructions that have structural elements in the form of tendons, such as cable-stayed bridges (Figure 1.12) or steel towers with anchorage. For example, the Normandy Bridge in France, with a span of 856 m, has, in addition to classical supporting tendons, active elements of the ATS type [10]. For civil constructions, active tendon systems can be used to reduce relative displacement levels (Figure 1.13). These systems can operate in both continuous and pulsed modes.
- **Active Bracing Systems** - are composed of hydraulic/electric actuation elements mounted within the bracing of a structural framework. Through these elements, using a control algorithm, judicious control forces are applied to reduce the structural response (Figure 1.14). Although initial experimental research conducted by [11] suggested that these systems have great potential for controlling structural systems, it has become evident that, with the development of semi-active control systems, they represent a more reliable solution.

Figure 1.12: Active tendon control system for suspension bridges

Figure 1.13: Active tendon control system for civil constructions

- Active Mass Systems** - are an advancement of passive tuned mass systems, involving the replacement of rigidity and damping components with an automatic adjustment mechanism. They utilize the inertial component of the mass to generate control forces via an actuator connected to the building's structural system. Given that TMD is effective only for reducing the response associated with the fundamental mode of vibration, the introduction of AMD naturally extends the effectiveness of the control system to higher modes of vibration. The first implementation of such a system was reported in 1991 at the Kyobashi Seiwa building in Tokyo. Two AMD devices were installed on the building's terrace: one weighing 4 tons to control translational motion and one weighing 1 ton to reduce torsion [13]. The goal of the control system's arrangement was to reduce the building's movement during strong wind actions and moderately severe earthquakes. The favorable behavior of the control system was confirmed by [14] following assessments conducted during an earthquake recorded at the site. A more recent implementation of this system is presented by the company TESolution for the control tower at Incheon

Figure 1.14: Active bracing control system, adapted from [12]

International Airport in South Korea (Figure 1.15).

Figure 1.15: a) Active mass system b) ⁸Example of an active mass mounted for the control tower at Incheon International Airport in South Korea

1.1.3 Semi-Active Control Systems

Semi-active control systems represent an extension of passive systems aimed at enhancing their performance by introducing the ability to adapt energy dissipation capacity according to the structural response. They combine the advantages of passive and active systems, consisting of a monitoring system, a control system, an actuation system, and a passive energy dissipation element.

⁸Photo source: http://www.tesolution.com/uploads/6/9/3/0/69304001/tesolution_e-brochure_20.pdf (accessed on 10.03.2023)

Unlike active systems, in semi-active systems, the actuation element does not directly apply forces to the structural framework but serves to adjust, in real time, the dissipation characteristics of a passive element. In this sense, the main advantage of semi-active systems is their ability to operate with significantly less energy than active systems, with the possibility of operating on batteries. This aspect is crucial as there is a high probability of power supply interruption during severe earthquakes.

On the other hand, one of the major limitations of this type of system is the limited capacity to implement control forces imposed by the constraints of passive devices.

The most common types of semi-active control systems include: *Semi-active Tuned Mass Systems*, *Semi-active Liquid Tuned Mass Systems*, *Semi-active Friction Dampers*, *Semi-active Hydraulic Dampers*, and *Semi-active Systems with Controllable Fluid*.

- **Semi-active Tuned Mass Systems** - are essentially tuned mass systems for which it is possible to modify the rigidity and/or damping characteristics in real-time. This feature allows for continuous adjustment of the system, maintaining its efficiency even when the structural characteristics change due to structural damage. One of the most recent implementations, carried out by Maurer [15], aims to adjust the behavior of a pendulum-type tuned mass using two semi-active dampers with magnetorheological fluid connected to the building's structural framework. Other significant approaches regarding the development of semi-active tuned mass systems have been proposed by [16], [17], [18], [19].

Figure 1.16: a) Danube City Tower, Vienna, Austria b) semi-active dampers positioned at the bottom of the pendulum-type tuned mass ⁹

- **Semi-active tuned liquid mass systems** - differ from passive tuned mass systems by incorporating equipment inside the active liquid reservoir that controls the fluid movement in real time. This is achieved through the use of automatic deflectors (Figure 1.17) [21], or valves that ensure liquid flow control [22], aimed at controlling the dynamic characteristics of the semi-active system. In alternative approaches [23], the introduction of a spring with an automatic stiffness adjustment mechanism outside the reservoir was proposed, while [24] studied the possibility of controlling the sloshing phenomenon using a magnetic fluid activated by an electromagnet.
- **Semi-active friction dampers** - utilize an automated system that adjusts in real time, based on the parameters of the structural response, the magnitude of the friction force

⁹photo source: sourced from [20]

Figure 1.17: Semi-active tuned liquid mass (proposed by [21])

at a passive element, which dissipates seismic energy through friction. This type of system employs electro-mechanical or piezoelectric actuating mechanisms that apply normal forces to the friction surface based on a control algorithm. The behavior of such equipment can be modeled, as described by [25], as an element with 3 nodes (Figure 1.18) and three degrees of freedom. The first and third nodes are connected to the degrees of freedom of the building, while the second node can be seen as a sliding joint. As long as it does not exceed the value $N(t) \cdot \mu$, the magnitude of the axial force in the element is given by the axial stiffness of the element (k) multiplied by the difference in displacement between nodes 1 and 3. Energy dissipation occurs when the friction force is reached, and the relative displacements from the sliding joint are mobilized.

Figure 1.18: Semi-active friction damper concept (adapted from [25])

- **Semi-active hydraulic dampers** - dissipate energy through dampers that operate using a hydraulic fluid, whose flow rate is controlled by an electromechanical valve (Figure 1.19). When the valve is closed, the damper operates as a structural element with constant stiffness. The controlled opening of the valve modifies the stiffness of the damper and facilitates energy dissipation based on the set flow rate. These types of systems have been practically applied for seismic protection of structures in Japan, including the Kajima Shizuoka building in Shizuoka City [26], whose steel frame was equipped with a system containing 8 hydraulic dampers, mounted within V-bracing. These were designed to develop a maximum damping force of 1000 kN.
- **Semi-active systems with controllable fluid** - utilize damping equipment that employs fluids capable of transitioning from a liquid state to a semi-solid state very quickly in the presence of an electric field (electrorheological fluids) or a magnetic field (magnetorheological fluids). The adjustment of the damping force of the damper is accomplished based

Figure 1.19: Semi-active hydraulic damper concept (adapted from [27])

on the intensity of the generated electric/magnetic field, by altering the viscosity of the fluid. As presented by [27], systems using magnetorheological fluid are more efficient for applications in civil engineering, capable of generating forces an order of magnitude higher than those using electrorheological fluid. Additionally, they can operate under a wide range of temperature conditions (-40° - 150°). The first building equipped with such a system is the National Museum of Emerging Science and Innovation in Tokyo, which has 2 magnetorheological dampers produced by Sanwa Tekki, capable of generating a maximum damping force of 300 kN. The advantage of systems with controllable fluid over other semi-active systems is that they do not require the installation of moving electromechanical parts to adjust the damping force, which translates to high reliability and lower maintenance costs. Among the most significant works related to this type of system are [28], [29], and [30].

Figure 1.20: a) Magnetorheological damper concept (adapted from [27]); b) Hysteretic behavior of magnetorheological damper (adapted from [31])

1.1.4 Hybrid control systems

Although the control systems presented above offer multiple possibilities for reducing building vibrations, hybrid control proposes the realization of a control system by assembling passive, active, or semi-active system components in parallel within the same structural frame.

Generally, hybrid control systems incorporate a passive element assisted by an active or semi-active element. This assembly has the advantage of operating in two modes: as a hybrid

system (generally in the case of low-magnitude earthquakes) or as a passive system (in the case of severe earthquakes). The transition from one operating mode to another occurs automatically, based on the structural response and seismic motion parameters. Furthermore, to reduce energy requirements, the actuating mechanisms in hybrid systems are sized to generate significantly lower control forces than if they were part of an active control system.

There is also the possibility of implementing a hybrid system composed of two passive systems. For example, for buildings equipped with base isolation systems, passive tuned mass or tuned liquid mass systems can be utilized to reduce the structural response generated by the action of strong winds [32].

The literature identifies three types of hybrid systems: *Hybrid mass systems*, *Base isolation hybrid systems*, and *Hybrid systems with dampers and actuators*.

- **Hybrid mass systems** - are among the most popular structural control systems, given the large number of practical implementations reported in the literature [33], [34]. Generally, these incorporate a tuned mass whose vibration is adjusted using an actuator [35] or an assembly composed of a tuned mass and an active mass [36]. The tuned mass system serves to control the fundamental modes of vibration while the active equipment is used to increase the effectiveness of the TMD to suppress vibrations associated with higher modes. Among the most recent implementations is the system developed by TESolution for the Technomart building in Seoul. This aims to control vertical vibrations caused by ongoing activities in the building and reduce the structural response generated by wind action (Figure 1.21). Additionally, hybrid mass systems have been implemented in the cases of the Canton Tower and Ping An Finance Center buildings in China, as described by [37] and [38] respectively.

Figure 1.21: a) Technomart building, Seoul (54 floors); b) hybrid mass system implemented for the Technomart building ¹⁰

- **Hybrid Base Isolation Systems** - are composed of a base isolation system arranged in parallel with a passive control system (viscous damper [39], tuned mass [40], liquid tuned mass [41]), active (active mass [40], actuator) or semi-active (magnetorheological damper [42], [43], [44]). Figure 1.22 a), b). Although base isolation systems have the most practical implementations for reducing the seismic response of buildings, the implementation

¹⁰photo source: <http://www.tesolution.com/technomart-885160.html> (accessed on 19.03.2023)

of an additional system aims to reduce excessive lateral displacements of the isolators, which can lead to their damage. One application of this type of system involves the Obayashi Corporation's Technical Research Institute, for which the Obayashi company implemented, in addition to the base isolation system, an actuator that ensures active control in parallel (Figure 1.22 c).

Figure 1.22: a) Hybrid base isolation system - experimental implementation from [45] b) magnetorheological damper implemented by [45] c) actuator for active control of the base isolation system - implemented by Obayashi [46]

- **Hybrid Systems with Dampers and Actuators** - are control systems that include both viscous dampers and automatic actuation elements (actuators), which can operate independently or in parallel to control the structural response. They can be arranged within the same structural element (for example, within a bracing system K , Figure 1.23) or in different areas of the structural framework. Hybrid systems with dampers and actuators have been extensively studied over the years by [47], [48], [49], and [50], with experimental results highlighting that they have higher efficiency than passive systems for reducing structural response, but also that to achieve the same performance, they require smaller control forces compared to active control systems.

1.2 Methodologies/Algorithms for Implementing Active Control

The previous section briefly presented the main structural control systems that can be implemented to reduce the seismic response of buildings. Passive systems, while having lower efficiency, are the most accessible and easiest to implement approaches, while semi-active and hybrid systems offer the advantage of a middle ground between effectiveness and resource requirements. Thus, active systems represent the ideal option for controlling the behavior of structures. In terms of effectiveness, they have the ability to adapt the implemented control forces

Figure 1.23: Concept of hybrid system with damper and actuator (proposed in [50])

to the requirements imposed by the structural response, thereby being capable of counteracting destructive effects for a wide range of actions and excitations. Although the high energy requirements for implementing control forces and the level of confidence in their reliability have led to a relatively low number of active control implementations in the last decade, recent technological advancements, especially regarding electric motors and energy storage equipment, are bringing these systems back to the forefront for research and large-scale implementation in the near future.

As previously mentioned, an active control system consists of three main subsystems that focus on: monitoring the structural response, calculating the actuation command using a control algorithm, and implementing control forces through execution elements (Figure 1.24). Given the purpose of this doctoral thesis, namely the study of the effectiveness of implementing active control for structural moment resisting - frames, it is necessary to develop integrated numerical models that can capture both the structural response and the effects of the control system's action. In this regard, within the numerical models commonly used by structural engineers, it is necessary to implement a control algorithm that uses the structural response to calculate, at each time step, the corresponding magnitude of the applied control forces. Thus, in the continuation of the content of this subsection, the main methodologies/algorithms used for implementing active control of buildings will be reviewed.

Looking at the overall evolution of research regarding the algorithms for active control of buildings, the late 1990s and early 2000s represent reference periods in which the subject enjoyed widespread popularity. However, numerous recent experimental studies and practical implementations suggest that the topic has once again become one of the main concerns of researchers in the field [34], [38], [51], [52], and [53]. Below are briefly presented the main methodologies addressed in the specialized literature:

1. **Active Structural Control through Judicious Pole Allocation**
2. **Independent Control of Modal Space**
3. **Active Structural Control through Successive Impulse**
4. **Sliding Mode Active Structural Control**
5. **Active Structural Control Using Fuzzy Logic**
6. **Market - Based Structural Control**

Figure 1.24: Conceptual diagram of an active control system

7. Optimal Structural Control

8. Instantaneous Optimal Structural Control

9. Active Structural Control Using Artificial Neural Networks

Since the concepts underlying active control of structures are inherently interdisciplinary, it is necessary to first reformulate the equations commonly used in building dynamics into an equivalent form that aligns with the conventions of the control system field before reviewing the corresponding control methodologies. Thus, the following presents the procedure for transitioning classical equation of motion to state-space format.

The motion of damped systems subjected to seismic excitations can be modeled by an inhomogeneous system of n second-order differential equations with constant coefficients, as presented in **Eq: 1.1**.

$$\mathbf{M} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{C} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{K}(t) \cdot \mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{h} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) \quad (1.1)$$

The components of **Eq: 1.1** can be divided into two categories:

1. Components that determine and describe the structural response:

- $\mathbf{u}(t)$ - the instantaneous displacement vector ($n \times 1$) response in the direction of the degrees of freedom (DOF);
- $\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t)$ - the instantaneous velocity vector response in the direction of the DOF;
- $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t)$ - the instantaneous acceleration vector response in the direction of the DOF;
- $\ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t)$ - the ground acceleration during the earthquake;
- \mathbf{h} - is a vector that serves to scale the ground acceleration in the direction of the DOF;

2. Components that describe the properties of the structural system:

- $\mathbf{K}(t)$ – is the stiffness matrix of the structure;
- \mathbf{M} – is the mass matrix of the structure;
- \mathbf{C} – is the damping matrix of the structure;

Multiplying **Eq: 1.1** by \mathbf{M}^{-1} and considering that the stiffness matrix is constant throughout the simulation, $\mathbf{K}(t) = \mathbf{K}$, results in:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{h} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) \quad (1.2)$$

Noting:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{u}_1(t) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) = \mathbf{u}_2(t) = \dot{\mathbf{u}}_1(t) \quad (1.4)$$

By identification, it results:

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}_1(t) = \mathbf{u}_2(t) \quad (1.5)$$

$$\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_2(t) = -\mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) - \mathbf{M}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{u}(t) - \mathbf{h} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) \quad (1.6)$$

Integrating in matrix form **Eq: 1.5** and **Eq: 1.6**:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{u}}_1(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{u}}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) \\ \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{O} & \mathbf{I} \\ -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{K} & -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{C} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ -\mathbf{h} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) \quad (1.7)$$

Noting:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) \\ \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{z}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{A} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{O} & \mathbf{I} \\ -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{K} & -\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{C} \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{F}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ -\mathbf{h} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) = \mathbf{H}\ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t); \end{aligned} \quad (1.8)$$

Rewriting **Eq: 1.7**, the equation of motion in state format results:

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (1.9)$$

This formulation is relatively new in the field of structural engineering, even though the mathematical model is frequently used in electrical engineering and automation. The main advantage of this expression is that the system of second-order differential equations is transformed into a system of first-order differential equations, which leads to obtaining an explicit time integration relationship, through which the structural response can be determined numerically. In **Eq: 1.9**, $\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t)$ and $\mathbf{z}(t)$ are called state variables and describe the dynamic model's response at a given moment in time.

Introducing the effect of control forces into **Eq: 1.9**:

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t) \quad (1.10)$$

Where:

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.11)$$

And the matrix \mathbf{D} serves to scale the control forces in the desired degrees of freedom.

1.2.1 Active Structural Control through Judicious Pole Placement

The controlled motion of a structural model with a finite number of degrees of freedom can be described by the system in **Eq: 1.12**. It is observed that, in addition to **Eq: 1.9**, an additional equation has been introduced. This serves to establish the relationship between the state variable and the measured output data (the measured structural response).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{z}(t) \end{cases} \quad (1.12)$$

Where \mathbf{C} is the output matrix.

Considering that the control force $\mathbf{f}_c(t)$ is dependent on the state vector, according to the relationship $\mathbf{f}_c(t) = \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t)$, where \mathbf{G} is the reaction matrix:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}\mathbf{z}(t) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{z}(t) \end{cases} \quad (1.13)$$

Equivalent to:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}) \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{z}(t) \end{cases} \quad (1.14)$$

Noting that $(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G}) = \mathbf{W}$ and substituting in **Eq: 1.14** results in:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{z}(t) \end{cases} \quad (1.15)$$

An equivalent representation of the system from relation **Eq: 1.14** is the input-output format in the frequency domain, using a transfer matrix. This is obtained by using the Laplace transform.

Figure 1.25: Transition from the time domain to frequency domain

Thus, **Eq: 1.14** becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{Z}(s) - \mathbf{z}(0) = \mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{Z}(s) + \mathbf{F}(s) \\ \mathbf{Y}(s) = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{Z}(s) \end{cases} \quad (1.16)$$

Considering that, before the incidence of seismic motion, the structural model is considered to be at rest, we can evaluate the initial state vector as being equal to zero $\mathbf{z}(0) = \mathbf{0}$.

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{Z}(s) - \mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{Z}(s) = \mathbf{F}(s) \\ \mathbf{Y}(s) = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{Z}(s) \end{cases} \quad (1.17)$$

Eq: uivalently:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{Z}(s) \cdot (\mathbf{sI} - \mathbf{W}) = \mathbf{F}(s) \\ \mathbf{Y}(s) = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{Z}(s) \end{cases} \quad (1.18)$$

Substituting $\mathbf{Z}(s)$ into the second equation results in:

$$\mathbf{Y}(s) = \mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{sI} - \mathbf{W})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{F}(s) \quad (1.19)$$

Noting $\mathbf{H}(s)$ as the transfer matrix of the model and considering that the matrix \mathbf{C} is equal to the identity matrix:

$$\mathbf{H}(s) = \frac{\mathbf{Y}(s)}{\mathbf{F}(s)} = (\mathbf{sI} - \mathbf{W})^{-1} = \frac{(\mathbf{sI} - \mathbf{W})^*}{|\mathbf{sI} - \mathbf{W}|} \quad (1.20)$$

By definition, the poles of the transfer matrix are those values of s for which $\mathbf{H}(s)$ tends to infinity. At the same time, the values of s for which $|\mathbf{sI} - \mathbf{W}| = 0$ represent the eigenvalues λ_i of the matrix \mathbf{W} . These describe the structural response, being related to the circular frequency ω_i and the critical damping ratios ζ_i associated with the vibration modes, in complex conjugate pairs. Thus, considering that $\mathbf{W} = (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{BG})$, structural control through judicious pole allocation implies controlling the behavior of the system/model by favorably adjusting the vibration characteristics associated with the significant modes affecting the structural response. Essentially, the eigenvalues of the matrix \mathbf{A} , which characterize the eigenmodes of the uncontrolled building, are conveniently modified by the judicious choice of the reaction matrix \mathbf{G} [54].

$$\lambda_i = \zeta_i \omega_i \pm i \omega_i \sqrt{1 - \zeta_i^2} \quad (1.21)$$

Numerous works that focused on this topic describe different methods for determining the command/reaction matrix. Among the early research, those by W. M. Wonham in 1967 [55] and E. J. Davison in 1970 [56] proposed that, for a system of the form **Eq: 1.22**, the input size should be $\mathbf{f}_c(t) = \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t)$. Defining $\mathbf{z}(t)$ as a vector of dimension n describing the system state, $\mathbf{f}_c(t)$ as a vector of dimension m representing the input size, and $\mathbf{y}(t)$ as the output size of dimension l , Wonham showed that, for the case where $l = m$ (the state size is completely measurable), the pair (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) is controllable if and only if, for an arbitrarily chosen set of values, there exists a constant matrix \mathbf{G} such that these represent the eigenvalues of the matrix $(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{BG})$. Davison generalized this result for situations where the rank of the matrix \mathbf{B} is $l \leq m$ ($\mathbf{f}_c(t) = \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{y}(t)$).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{z}(t) \end{cases} \quad (1.22)$$

In 1972, O. A. Solheim [57] proposed a new method for determining the reaction matrix \mathbf{G} ($\mathbf{f}_c(t) = \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{y}(t)$), combining the main approaches up to that time, namely:

- Calculate the \mathbf{G} matrix such that it minimizes a quality index (cost function) expressed through a quadratic functional of states and inputs.

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t [\mathbf{z}(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{f}_c(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{f}_c(t)] dt \quad (1.23)$$

- Determine the matrix \mathbf{G} such that the system $\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t)$ has predetermined eigenvalues.

He emphasized that, in the case of the first approach, the constant matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} generate a unique set of eigenvalues for $(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{G})$, which does not necessarily guarantee the desired degree of stability. On the other hand, the second method ensures system stability by judiciously choosing the poles of the transfer function. However, in most cases, since the matrix \mathbf{G} is not unique, a "favorable" choice of it is necessary. Therefore, Solheim proposes a new method that encompasses both approaches and involves determining the reaction matrix such that, on the one hand, it ensures certain eigenvalues, and on the other hand, minimizes the quadratic functional. Specifically, this materializes through finding the tuning matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} , corresponding to a predetermined set of eigenvalues.

Other important contributions to the development and understanding of these system control techniques were made by the works published by W.L. Brogan in 1974 [58], H. Kimura in 1975 [59], B. C. Moore in 1976 [60], O. A. Sebakhy, and N.N. Sorial in 1979 [61].

The application of these techniques in the field of structural engineering has its beginnings in "Modal control of multistory structures" published by Martin R. C. and Soong T. T. in 1976 [62]. Other representative works include those developed by P. C. Wang et al. in 1983 [63], H.H.E. Leipholz and M. Abdel-Rohman in 1986 [64], and T.T. Soong in 1992 [65]. Among the most recent references are N. G. Pnevmatikos and C. J. Gantes in 2006 [66], who proposed the implementation of a control strategy based on the distribution of the eigenvalues of the system according to the frequency content of seismic excitation, N. G. Pnevmatikos in 2017 [67], who presented a new algorithm for determining the reaction matrix, as well as the works [68], [69].

1.2.2 Independent Control of Modal Space

This control method involves, through the introduction of the modal matrix Φ and the modal coordinates $\mathbf{q}(t)$, decoupling the system vibrations into independent modes and applying the control strategy distinctly for each. Thus, starting from the equation of motion of a controlled structural model, described by a system of linear second-order differential equations with constant, non-homogeneous coefficients that are dependent on each other **Eq: 1.24**.

$$\mathbf{M} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{C} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{K}(t) \cdot \mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{h} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) + \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{f}_c(t) \quad (1.24)$$

Noting:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) &= \Phi \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) &= \Phi \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) \\ \mathbf{u}(t) &= \Phi \cdot \mathbf{q}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (1.25)$$

The modal matrix composed of the eigenvectors has the form:

$$\Phi = [\phi_1 \ \phi_2 \ \dots \ \phi_{n-1} \ \phi_n] \quad (1.26)$$

Considering the eigenvectors to be orthogonal with respect to the stiffness, inertia, and damping matrices, r and s representing the number corresponding to the vibration mode:

$$\phi_r^T \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \phi_s = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } r \neq s \\ m_i^*, & \text{if } r = s \end{cases} \quad (1.27)$$

$$\phi_r^T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \phi_s = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } r \neq s \\ k_i^*, & \text{if } r = s \end{cases} \quad (1.28)$$

$$\phi_r^T \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \phi_s = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } r \neq s \\ c_i^*, & \text{if } r = s \end{cases} \quad (1.29)$$

Replacing **Eq: 1.26** in **Eq: 1.24** and multiplying from the left by Φ^{-1} results in:

$$\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \Phi \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \Phi \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \Phi \cdot \mathbf{q}(t) = -\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{h} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) + \Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{f}_c(t) \quad (1.30)$$

Considering that $(\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \Phi)$, $(\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \Phi)$, and $(\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \Phi)$ are diagonal matrices with components m_i^* , c_i^* , and k_i^* , one can arrive at the relationship:

$$\ddot{q}_i(t) + 2 \cdot \zeta_i \omega_i \dot{q}_i(t) + \omega_i^2 q_i(t) = -\Gamma_i \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_g(t) + v_i(t) \quad (1.31)$$

where:

$$\Gamma = \frac{\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{h}}{\phi_i^T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \phi_i} \quad (1.32)$$

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \frac{\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{D}}{\phi_i^T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \phi_i} \cdot \mathbf{f}_c(t) = [v_1 \ v_2 \ \dots \ v_{n-1} \ v_n] \quad (1.33)$$

and Γ is the matrix that contains the mass activated independently on each vibration mode, $v(t)$ being the vector of control forces in the modal space.

It is observed that the system remains coupled through the control component, as the value of $v(t)_i$ depends on multiple modal coordinates. However, if $v(t)_i$ is defined according to [9], based on $\dot{q}_i(t)$ and $q_i(t)$, the equations become independent and can be treated separately for each vibration mode.

The optimal modal control forces $v(t)$ can be obtained by minimizing the functional:

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^n J_i \quad (1.34)$$

where J_i is a cost function that can take the form [9]:

$$J_i = \int_0^t [Q_{1i} \cdot q_i(t)^2 + Q_{2i} \cdot \dot{q}_i(t)^2 + R_i \cdot v_i(t)^2] dt \quad (1.35)$$

The control force can be obtained using **Eq: 1.36**:

$$\mathbf{f}_c(t) = \left(\frac{\Phi^T \cdot \mathbf{D}}{\phi_i^T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \phi_i} \right)^{-1} \cdot v(t) \quad (1.36)$$

It should be noted that this method is effective only when there are a limited number of vibration modes that influence the structural response.

This methodology was initially proposed by L. Meirovitch et al. in 1977 in [70] and [71] for applications in the aerospace field and for certain distributed gyroscopic systems. In [72], the method is specialized for the dynamics of structures subjected to seismic excitations. Additionally, analyzing **Eq: 1.33** from the perspective of the number of actuating devices associated with the controlled modes, [9] concludes that the most appropriate choice is to set the number of controllers equal to the number of considered modes. Recently, alternative approaches have also been proposed by [73], [74], and [75].

From an experimental perspective, A. Baz et al. [76] analyzed the response of a single-degree-of-freedom system, proposing a modified version of the method that incorporates energy criteria for calculating the control forces.

1.2.3 Active Structural Control through Successive Impulses

During dynamic loading, the response of a structure transitions between the elastic behavior zone and the inelastic behavior zone. Structural control through the application of successive impulses proposes an approach based on the efficiency of using energy to apply control forces, namely activating the control mechanism only when the state variables reach a certain value. The fundamental idea of this technique is to apply a train of forces (impulses), which aim to keep the response of the structural system within certain parameters (Figure 1.26). For buildings, these can be determined based on displacements/angular drifts or absolute level accelerations. In the case of violent seismic excitations, the main objective becomes maintaining structural elements within the linear behavior domain or limiting, as much as possible, the structural damage.

Figure 1.26: Structural control through the application of successive impulses

In 1981, F.E. Udwadia et al.[77], utilizing modal decomposition and superimposing the effect of control forces in the equation of motion, proposed a method for determining the impulse vector, such that the functional $J(t)$ in relation **Eq: 1.37** is minimized. A criterion based on velocities and displacements was used to calculate the response ceiling threshold.

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T_p} [\mathbf{q}(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{A}_1 \cdot \mathbf{q}(t) + \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{A}_2 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)] dt \quad (1.37)$$

Where $\mathbf{q}(t)$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)$ are modal coordinates, t_0 is the time step at which the structural response meets the ceiling criteria, and T_p is the time interval during which control forces (impulses) are applied.

S.F. Masri et al. [78] published a similar approach in the same year. They proposed a cost function that can encompass potential deformation energy or the kinetic energy of the system. Additionally, they performed a simulation regarding the efficiency of the arrangement of actuating devices. Using a model with three degrees of freedom, they analyzed the response of the controlled system, both sequentially and simultaneously, in the direction of each dynamic

coordinate. The results showed that for the analyzed model, positioning the actuating device at the top level represents the most energy-efficient option.

A.M. Reinhorn et al. [79] studied the application of this control methodology in structures considered to exhibit inelastic behavior and that can be modeled as single-degree-of-freedom systems. They considered implementing a strategy based on associating the Newmark-beta numerical integration method with the Newton-Raphson method.

In 1988, R.K. Miller et al. [80] demonstrated the effectiveness of the methodology in an experimental study using a reduced model of a six-story structure, with a floor height of 0.3 m and plan dimensions of 0.61 m x 0.91 m. The actuating devices, using compressed air, were placed at the top level along with the structural response measurement sensor and the external force application mechanism. The control strategy proposed by them is based on applying impulses in the direction of the degrees of freedom where the velocity reaches a maximum value. In this regard, control impulses are applied when the relative displacement changes sign and are calculated based on **Eq: 1.38**.

$$p_i(t) = \begin{cases} -c_i \cdot \text{sgn}(v_i) \cdot |v_i|^{n_i}, & \text{if } t_{0i} \leq t \leq (t_{0i} + T_{di}) \\ 0, & \text{if } (t_{0i} + T_{di}) < t < t_{0i} \end{cases} \quad (1.38)$$

Where c_i is a scaling coefficient, v_i is the absolute or relative velocity at point i , n_i is a power considered for the velocity at point i , t_{0i} is the time at which point i has a displacement of 0, and T_{di} is the duration of the action. It can be observed that the method presented above does not depend on knowledge of the structure's characteristics (**M, C, K**) nor on the influence of incursions into the plastic domain. Other approaches combining optimal instantaneous control methods and the use of artificial neural networks have been proposed by C.P. Pantelides et al. [81] and S-L Hung et al. [82].

1.2.4 Sliding Mode Active Structural Control

The method of controlling systems in sliding mode (sliding mode control - SMC) has been developed for application in nonlinear systems, providing robustness against parametric uncertainties. The strategy is based on discontinuous control and aims to steer and maintain the trajectories of state variables toward a suitably chosen surface, called the sliding surface. Determination of the control law occurs in two steps.

1. A sliding surface (sliding function) is established that generates an appropriate response, restricting the system's trajectory along it.
2. The command is determined so that the state trajectories of the system are brought to and maintained on the sliding surface.

Thus, a system, starting from non-zero initial conditions, can be in two situations: either driving toward the sliding surface or on the sliding surface, following its dynamics.

Among the first reference works addressing this control strategy are those of V. Utkin (1977) [83], E. Slotine [84], and K. Furuta [85]. In the case of structures exhibiting linear and nonlinear behavior subjected to seismic excitations, sliding mode control has been described in detail by J. N. Yang et al. in Technical Report NCEER-94-0017 [86]. Starting from the state-space equation of motion **Eq: 1.39**, they define the sliding surface s as a linear combination of the state variables, $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) = 0$, where $\mathbf{s} = [s_1 \ s_2 \ \dots \ s_{r-1} \ s_r]$, r is the number of controllers, and P of size $(r \times 2n)$ is determined such that motion on the surface is stable.

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t) \quad (1.39)$$

To determine the equation of motion on the sliding surface, the effect of the external action $\mathbf{F}(t)$ is neglected, but is being considered to calculate the control law that drives the motion

Figure 1.27: Control methodology concept - SMC

toward the sliding surface. Additionally, considering $\dot{s} = 0$, the equivalent control force corresponding to the sliding surface is obtained:

$$\dot{s} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) \rightarrow \dot{s} = \mathbf{P} \cdot (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t)) = 0 \rightarrow \mathbf{f}_{ceq} = -(\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{B})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) \quad (1.40)$$

Substituting into **Eq: 1.39**, the equation of motion that characterizes the system's dynamics on the sliding surface is determined:

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = (\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{B})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{A}) \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) \quad (1.41)$$

The matrix \mathbf{P} is determined using the reduction of the system formed by the state equations to a regular form, as proposed by Utkin [87], along with the use of a cost function.

The control component that drives the motion toward the sliding surface $S = 0$ is determined using a Lyapunov function $\mathbf{V} = 0.5 \cdot \mathbf{s}^T \cdot \mathbf{s} = 0$.

Additionally, the paper presents a similar algorithm for the case of nonlinear systems.

R. Adhikari et al. [88] applied the SMC strategy for controlling building structures with an active mass, opting for a control force of the following form $\mathbf{f}_c(t, \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{f}_{ceq}(t, \mathbf{z}) + \eta \cdot \text{sgn}(\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{z}))$, where $\eta \cdot \text{sgn}(\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{z}))$ represents the nonlinear component of the controller. S. Sarbjeet et al. [89] proposed a control algorithm based on SMC for the control of frame structures, considering uncertainties related to seismic excitation. In 2005, H. Alli et al. [90] proposed the use of fuzzy rules to drive the trajectory of state variables toward the sliding surface \mathbf{s} , while N. G. Pnevmatikos et al. [91] present a new method for determining the sliding surface based on the judicious allocation of poles according to the frequency content of seismic motion. In a more recent paper, M. Khatibinia et al. [92] (2020) present a method for optimal control in sliding mode. The authors propose the condition in **Eq: 1.42**, which forces the trajectories of state variables toward the sliding surface, using a cost function to determine the matrix \mathbf{P} ($\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) = 0$).

$$0.5 \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{s}^2 \leq -\gamma |\mathbf{s}| \quad (1.42)$$

where γ is a constant value greater than zero. Other dedicated works that present the issues of SMC in detail are V.I. Utkin [87], C. Edwards [93], Wilfrid Perruquetti et al. [94], Y. Shtessel et al. [95], F. Leyla et al. [96], and S. Husain et al. [97].

1.2.5 Active Structural Control Using Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic is an extended logic that encompasses partial truth, meaning values that range between completely true and completely false. The essence of fuzzy logic is best described by its founder, L.A. Zadeh, in the work [98], „Unlike traditional logical systems, fuzzy logic is aimed at providing a model for modes of reasoning which are approximate rather than exact. In this perspective, the importance of fuzzy logic derives from the fact that almost all of human reasoning—and especially commonsense reasoning—is approximate in nature.”

Thus, the expression true/false, characterizing the state of a system at a given moment, can be encompassed in qualitative expressions. For example, for a resilient structure, it can be stated that the top displacement is LARGE if it exceeds 15 cm. In fuzzy logic, for a displacement less than 15 cm, a membership function $\mu(x)$ is defined, which takes values between 0 and 1 and serves to characterize the degree of membership of the value to the defined set. Thus, for $x = 12$, $\mu(12)$ can be evaluated at 0.75, and we can say that the statement “the building has a LARGE displacement” is true to 75%.

Therefore, we can say that fuzzy logic control (FLC) models more the decision-making behavior of a human operator than the evolution of the system. Consequently, FLC generally lacks an objective character, considering that humans are not an optimal decision-making system.

Figure 1.28: Concept of fuzzy logic

One of the first approaches regarding the control of resilient structures using fuzzy logic was proposed by F. Casciati et al. [99] in 1994, who theoretically analyzed the seismic response of a two-degree-of-freedom system using a controller characterized by 18 fuzzy rules, with 3 membership functions for the input variables (displacement and velocity) and 5 for the output variables (control force). Defuzzification was performed using the centroid method, and inference was done using Larsen’s product rule in generalized modus ponens. Yu Tang [100] developed a comprehensive paper detailing the fuzzy control methodology and its application for controlling a single-degree-of-freedom system. The results obtained are compared with those experimentally determined by L.L. Chung et al. [101]. Figure 1.29 highlights the control strategy proposed by him.

Figure 1.29: Concept of fuzzy logic (from [100])

Additionally, L. Faravelli et al. [102] proposed the use of neural networks for adapting the membership functions and fuzzy rules of the controller, aiming to reduce the structural response; thus, after determining the output, the output error is evaluated, which is used to establish a new membership function or a fuzzy rule to influence the system in an appropriate manner. Battaini et al. [103] presented the implementation of FLC for controlling a three-story frame structure. They used an active mass as the actuating element, and the system response was measured using a limited number of sensors. Moreover, the issue of controller stability is also addressed in this work. A. Tani et al. [104] utilized neural networks to estimate the peak values of displacements, control forces, and the actuator's stroke for a model with 5 degrees of freedom, in order to optimize the process of determining the membership functions within a FLC.

In 2004, M. Al-Dawod et al. [105] studied the efficiency of applying fuzzy logic control for systems with inelastic behavior, using the benchmark criteria proposed by Y. Ohtori et al. [106]. Following the analysis of the structural response, considering 10 seismic motions, it was concluded that the effectiveness of FLC largely depends on the characteristics of the seismic excitation considered in the design of the controller.

Other important references include: C.B. Brown et al. [107], H. Kawamura et al. [108], [109], T-L Teng et al. [110], K-M Choi et al. [111], S. Pourzeynali et al. [112], and N. D. Anh et al. [113], X. Kang et al. [114], A. Zamani et al. [115], and M. Amini et al. [116].

1.2.6 Market-Based Structural Control

Market-Based Control (MBC) is based on the idea of transitioning from a centralized control system to a decentralized control system, analogous to the economic efficiency of the two approaches. In the case of a centralized control strategy, a control system utilizes the entirety of information received from sensors and, based on calculations, determines control forces in specified directions. In a decentralized system, each actuating device has the capacity to correlate the information received from sensors and generate an appropriate control force. The implementation of this approach starts from the idea of allocating the system's control resources in an efficient manner.

If in the economic market, goods and services represent the subject of transactions, in structural control, the essential resource is the power allocated to each device. In the dynamics of the economic market, traders aim to maximize profit, while buyers aim to maximize utility (ef-

iciency). Similarly, within a system, each power source has an associated cost function that depends on the price and power produced at each time step and accounts for the profit obtained. At the same time, actuating devices (buyers) have an associated cost function that depends on the structural response of the associated subsystem, the amount of power, and its price. The price is established based on supply and demand.

Although from the perspective of individual profit, traders and buyers tend to maximize the value of the cost function concerning the power sold/bought, a general optimization of the function values is necessary. In this sense, the market serves to aggregate the total individual demand to generate a demand function that characterizes the entire market. In the same way, a global supply function is defined. Thus, at every moment in time, demand and supply have a common intersection point that defines the price of energy. This point is called the optimal Pareto equilibrium point and represents the situation where the values of the cost functions cannot simultaneously increase for each agent.

These elements are detailed by J. P. Lynch and K. H. Law in several papers [117], [118], [119], [120]. One of their proposals for semi-active control of linear systems with one degree of freedom models demand and supply as functions in the following form:

$$P_{demand}(t) = |f(u(t), \dot{u}(t))| \cdot p + |g(u(t), \dot{u}(t))| \quad (1.43)$$

where P_{demand} is the power requested by the actuating device, and:

$$f(u, \dot{u}) = \frac{1}{T \cdot u(t) + Q \cdot \dot{u}(t)} \quad (1.44)$$

$$g(u, \dot{u}) = R \cdot u(t) + S \cdot \dot{u}(t) \quad (1.45)$$

where T, Q, R, S are constant tuning parameters of the controller and p is the price.

Regarding the offered power, it can be defined using **Eq: 1.46**

$$P_{demand}(t) = \frac{1}{\beta} \cdot p \quad (1.46)$$

where β is the tuning constant of the controller.

At the equilibrium point, the requested power is equal to the offered power, $P_{demand} = P_{offer}$. Thus, the equilibrium price can be obtained to determine the amount of power, using **Eq: 1.43**. The control force is obtained by applying a proportionality coefficient K to the quantity of power purchased [117].

$$f_c(t) = K \cdot \left(\frac{|R \cdot u(t) + S \cdot \dot{u}(t)|}{|T \cdot u(t) + Q \cdot \dot{u}(t)| + \beta} T \cdot u(t) + \frac{|R \cdot u(t) + S \cdot \dot{u}(t)|}{|T \cdot u(t) + Q \cdot \dot{u}(t)| + \beta} Q \cdot \dot{u}(t) \right) \quad (1.47)$$

Additionally, for systems with multiple degrees of freedom, the relationship in **Eq: 1.43** is modified by multiplying, for each actuating device, by a coefficient W_i , which represents the budget allocated to each buyer based on the importance assigned to them.

Furthermore, L. Gang et al. [121] proposed the implementation of the Force Analogy Method within MBC, which introduces the effect of the inelastic behavior of structural elements.

1.2.7 Optimal Structural Control

Considering that a control system has a limited amount of energy and certain technological constraints regarding the possibility of applying control forces, the issue of obtaining the best response using minimal resources arises. Thus, controlling structural response transforms into

an optimization problem that requires the application of optimal control methods. An optimal control problem often has the following general form [122]:

Determine $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1 \ x_2 \ \dots \ x_{n-1} \ x_n\}$ for which the value of the function $f(\mathbf{x})$ is minimized, such that:

$$\begin{aligned} g_j(x) &\leq 0, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ l_j(x) &= 0, j = 1, 2, \dots, p \end{aligned} \quad (1.48)$$

Where \mathbf{x} is a vector of dimension $(nx1)$, $f(\mathbf{x})$ is the objective function, which reflects the quantities of interest, and $g_j(x)$ and $l_j(x)$ are functions that define the constraints, meaning that only those values of \mathbf{x} that satisfy them will be considered acceptable for a minimum $f(\mathbf{x})$.

In controlling structural response, optimization can be facilitated by using a cost function $J(t)$, having the form of **Eq: 1.49**, according to [9]. Here, J_1 introduces the boundary conditions (related to the initial and final state) of the system, while J_2 represents the quantity evaluated over the entire time interval, depending on the system state and control forces.

$$J(t) = J_1(\mathbf{z}(t_0), \mathbf{z}(t_f)) + \int_{t_0}^{t_f} J_2(\mathbf{z}(t), \mathbf{f}_c(t)) dt \quad (1.49)$$

Assuming that, before and after an earthquake occurs, the building is at rest, the cost function can take the following form [9]:

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t [\mathbf{z}(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{f}_c(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{f}_c(t)] dt \quad (1.50)$$

Where \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are tuning matrices of the desired performance standard, being positive definite. For example, if a response with minimal displacements is desired, the values of matrix \mathbf{Q} will be greater than those of \mathbf{R} , resulting in large control forces.

Thus, the optimization problem essentially involves deriving the law for determining the vector of control forces $\mathbf{f}_c(t)$ such that, at each time step, $J(t)$ is minimized. The optimal values obtained must satisfy the equation of motion that characterizes the dynamics of the process; therefore, the solution to the differential equation in **Eq: 1.39**, $\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t)$, becomes the relationship that defines the constraints of the system.

The classical approach for determining control forces initially assumes calculating the solution to the differential equation and transitioning from the continuous domain to the discrete domain, obtaining the numerical integration relationship [123] **Eq: 1.51**:

$$\mathbf{z}_{k+1} = e^{\mathbf{A} \cdot \Delta t} \cdot \mathbf{z}_k + e^{\mathbf{A} \cdot \Delta t} \cdot \mathbf{H} \cdot \Delta t \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_{gk} + e^{\mathbf{A} \cdot \Delta t} \cdot \mathbf{B} \cdot \Delta t \cdot \mathbf{f}_{ck} \quad (1.51)$$

Noting:

$$e^{\mathbf{A} \cdot \Delta t} = \mathbf{F}_s \quad (1.52)$$

$$e^{\mathbf{A} \cdot \Delta t} \cdot \mathbf{H} \cdot \Delta t = \mathbf{H}_d \quad (1.53)$$

$$e^{\mathbf{A} \cdot \Delta t} \cdot \mathbf{B} \cdot \Delta t = \mathbf{G} \quad (1.54)$$

Eq: 1.51 becomes:

$$\mathbf{z}_{k+1} = \mathbf{F}_s \cdot \mathbf{z}_k + \mathbf{H}_d \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_{gk} + \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{f}_{ck} \quad (1.55)$$

To determine the minimum of the cost function **Eq: 1.50**, taking into account the constraints imposed by the explicit integration relationship **Eq: 1.55**, the method of Lagrange multipliers is used, defining the Lagrangian $L(\mathbf{z}_k, \mathbf{f}_{ck}, \lambda_{k+1})$ whose variation must equal 0 [123].

$$\delta L = \delta \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{z}_k^T \cdot \mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{z}_k + \mathbf{f}_{ck}^T \cdot \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{f}_{ck}) + \lambda_{k+1} \cdot (\mathbf{F}_s \cdot \mathbf{z}_k + \mathbf{H}_d \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{a}}_{gk} + \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{f}_{ck} - \mathbf{z}_{k+1}) \right) \quad (1.56)$$

Where: N is the number of steps over which the optimization is performed, and $\lambda_{k+1} = [\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \dots \lambda_{2n-1} \lambda_{2n}]^T$ is the Lagrange multiplier.

Considering that the control algorithm is in a closed loop $\lambda_k = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{z}_k$, the relationship for determining the control forces at each time step can be calculated:

$$\mathbf{f}_{ck} = -(\mathbf{G}^T \cdot \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{R})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{G}^T \cdot \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{F}_s \cdot \mathbf{z}_k \quad (1.57)$$

where \mathbf{P} is the solution of the Riccati equation of the form [123]: $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{F}_s^T \cdot \mathbf{P} \cdot (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{G} \cdot \mathbf{R}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{G}^T \cdot \mathbf{P})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{F}_s$

From the perspective of references, this subject enjoys high popularity, being discussed in many research papers, including those by M. Abdel-Rohman et al. [124], H. H. E. Leipholz et al. [64], J. Z. Cha et al. [125], H. T. Y. Yang et al. [126], B. J. N. Yang et al. [127], Z. Wu et al. [128], and D.P. Tomasula et al. [129].

1.2.8 Instantaneous Optimal Structural Control

Compared to optimal control, within this control methodology, the control forces are obtained by instantaneous minimization, at each time step t , $t_0 \leq t \leq t_f$, of a cost function $J(t)$ that can take the following form [130]:

$$J(t) = \mathbf{z}(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{Q} \cdot \mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{f}_c(t)^T \cdot \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{f}_c(t) \quad (1.58)$$

Using the modal matrix \mathbf{T} , associated with the eigenvectors of the state matrix \mathbf{A} , the corresponding modal state coordinates $\mathbf{q}_A(t)$, and noting $\mathbf{z}(t) = \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{q}_A(t)$ in the equation $\dot{\mathbf{z}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{z}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t)$, we can obtain:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_A(t) = \mathbf{\Lambda} \cdot \mathbf{q}_A(t) + \mathbf{T}^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t)) \quad (1.59)$$

Where $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{A}\mathbf{T}^{-1}$

Considering $\mathbf{q}(0) = 0$ over a short time interval Δt , the modal state vector can be determined with the relationship:

$$\mathbf{q}_A(t) = \int_0^{t-\Delta t} e^{\mathbf{\Lambda}(t-\tau)} \cdot \mathbf{T}^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{F}(\tau) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(\tau)) d\tau + \int_{t-\Delta t}^t e^{\mathbf{\Lambda}(t-\tau)} \cdot \mathbf{T}^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{F}(\tau) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(\tau)) d\tau \quad (1.60)$$

Thus, for the state vector, the following expression is obtained:

$$\mathbf{z}(t) = \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{D}(t - \Delta t) + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t)) \quad (1.61)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{D}(t - \Delta t) = e^{\mathbf{\Lambda}\Delta t} \cdot \mathbf{T}^{-1} \left(\mathbf{z}(t - \Delta t) + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{F}(t - \Delta t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}_c(t - \Delta t)) \right) \quad (1.62)$$

The determination of control forces is done in a manner similar to optimal control, computing the control law in both open and closed loops.

In 1992, J. N. Yang et al. [131] investigated how to choose the matrix \mathbf{Q} in order to guarantee the stability of the process. The same authors applied the method of instantaneous optimal control for structures with nonlinear behavior [132]. K. K. F. Wong et al. [133] proposed using the Force Analogy Method within this control strategy to introduce the effect of inelastic behavior. Other approaches were proposed by C.C. Chang et al. [134] and O. Bahar et al.[135], who used classical numerical integration methods, Newark and Wilson-, respectively, to solve

the system of differential equations characterizing motion. A more recent approach regarding the implementation of instantaneous optimal control is proposed by [136].

Also, another important work is that published by R.C. Lin et al. [137], which presents experimental results obtained by analyzing the response of a single-degree-of-freedom structure subjected to seismic action using a shaking table. They concluded that it is feasible to implement instantaneous optimal control within single-degree-of-freedom structures. It was also noted that the values of the structural response are very close to those obtained using classical/global optimal control.

1.2.9 Active Structural Control Using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)

Artificial neural networks are defined in analogy with the functioning of the human brain and represent systems that can perform specific tasks by adapting their internal operating rules through learning. Figure 1.30 presents the conceptual structure of an ANN.

Figure 1.30: Neural Network (concept)

Each unit in the input layer receives information from sensors, which it transmits to the units in the hidden layers. At this level, the information is processed and transmitted further to the units in the output layer, which connect to the actuation element. Additionally, the connections between units are characterized, depending on their importance, by certain weights W , which represent the essential elements of the learning process.

Among the first works that present the implementation of structural control based on artificial neural networks are those of L. Faravelli et al. [138] and Y.-K. Wan et al. [139]. They approached the subject in a similar manner. Initially, the control algorithm uses as input data the information obtained from sensors (the state variable at different time steps, along with the control force from the previous step). Then, after traversing the network, the output layer generates input data for the actuation devices, which apply the control forces. To train the ANN controller, a neural emulator network was introduced, which connects the input generated by the actuation device and the output represented by the measurements from the sensors.

Additionally, J. Ghaboussi et al. [140] proposed a control strategy that takes into account the dynamic coupling between the structure and the actuation devices and utilizes a variable number of units in the hidden layer, depending on necessity. A "quickprop" type algorithm was used for learning. Furthermore, K. Bani-Hani et al. [141] developed this neurocontroller for cases where the nonlinear behavior of the system is considered.

T.J. Kim et al. [142] proposed implementing an optimal method for adjusting the weights of the neural network. They used a cost function that incorporates the state vector and the control force vector, eliminating the need for empirical determination of a standard for the structural response.

A different approach was proposed by M. M. Rao et al. [143]. They developed a control algorithm that manages the natural modes of vibration with significant influence on the structural response. The control strategy uses two sets of artificial neural networks. The first set is used to obtain generalized accelerations for each considered vibration mode, utilizing the accelerations measured at specific points and the seismic excitation. In other words, the first set aims to determine the modal properties of the structure using the measurements of the structural response. The second set uses the generalized accelerations and the seismic input to calculate the control forces. Additionally, the control methodology is numerically applied to a ten-story structural system.

Other works addressing the subject include those by S. Saad et al. [144], T.K. Lin et al. [145], Y.A. He et al. [146], Y. Tang et al. [147], S.K. Chang et al. [148], Z. Khaled et al. [149], and T.Yu et al. [150].

1.3 Discussions/Conclusions Regarding the State of Research in Active Structural Control

The diversity of approaches presented highlights the ongoing concern of researchers and engineers towards the development and implementation of structural control to enhance the dynamic performance of buildings.

Regarding the control methodologies presented, it can be observed that most of them are implemented for simplified numerical models, with a limited number of degrees of freedom, elastic behavior, and where all values in the state vector are considered known/measurable. Furthermore, most of the listed methodologies utilize modeled dynamic characteristics (inertia matrix, stiffness matrix, damping matrix) for determining control forces. In reality, however, structures are complex systems with nonlinear behavior under seismic incidence, for which it is necessary to use elaborate numerical models to accurately estimate the seismic response. At the same time, measuring the structural response can be performed with a limited number of sensors, placed in specific areas of interest, and the numerical modeling of the dynamic characteristics of buildings is of an estimative nature.

In this sense, the innovative elements proposed in the doctoral thesis, which contribute to expanding knowledge in the field of active control, involve the development and simulation of complex numerical models (2D and 3D) that consider the inelastic behavior of structural elements and that have implemented control algorithms that operate independently of the variation of building characteristics using a reduced number of states.

Additionally, it should be noted that, besides the nine classical approaches to structural control presented, the specialized literature continues to propose other methodologies, such as those presented by [151] and [152], some of which are still in the early research phases for application in active control of buildings.

From a practical implementation perspective, until now, active control has been applied in reality to a limited number of buildings. In most cases, these control systems are used to reduce the structural response generated only by wind actions and earthquakes with a low recurrence interval. Recently, [34] conducted a significant study that includes a systematic evaluation of the literature regarding practical applications where structural control has been implemented. They show that out of a total of 208 identified applications, 57.7% of the control systems are located in Asia, 22.1% in America (Latin and North), 17.3% in Europe, 2.4% in Australia, and 0.5% in

Africa. Furthermore, the authors show that 47% of the systems were implemented before the year 2000, of which 7% (7 applications) were active systems, while 53% were implemented after 2000, of which 0.9% (one application) were active systems. Thus, the eight applications of active structural control were identified by them and are presented in Table 1.1. It should be mentioned that these include only control systems with active mass. Additionally, they identified 14 cases where structural control was implemented using a hybrid system (composed of a passive component (TMD) and an active one (AMD)).

Table 1.1: **Applications of Active Control - Active Mass Systems**

Building	Control Algorithm	Country
Kyobashi Seiwa Building	Optimal control	Japan
Riverside Sumida Building	Optimal control	Japan
Nanjing Communication Tower	Optimal control	China
Sendagaya INTES Building	Optimal control	Japan
Applause Tower	Optimal control	Japan
Porte Kanazawa	Optimal control	Japan
Herbis Osaka	Optimal control	Japan
Kingkey Finance Tower	Optimal control Control through judicious placement of poles Fuzzy-Neural Networks	China

They also present a discussion that starts from the question "**Are the research results in structural control applied in industry?**" from which the following points can be noted regarding active control:

- Although there are numerous theoretical studies related to modern algorithms for implementing active control, in industry there is a preference for using classical optimal control algorithms. Thus, there is a reluctance to adopt new control algorithms proposed by research initiatives.
- Despite the superior performance of active or hybrid systems, the reason they are not used to the same extent as passive systems is the large amount of energy required for operation, as well as the fact that they involve the use of high-capacity actuation devices, which incur significant additional costs.
- Although there is no clear evidence in this regard, another reason why their implementation is not popular may be the malfunctioning of existing systems during extreme events they have undergone. Additionally, although there are works in the specialized literature regarding the behavior of active systems, they do not detail the elements related to their actual performance, possible improper operations, or the costs of implementation and maintenance required. Moreover, as mentioned by [153], disseminating data regarding the performance of active control systems in real situations would lead to increased confidence in their large-scale implementation.
- To date, there are no technical prescriptions regarding the implementation of active systems, and the practical applications realized so far have been based on very specific approaches.
- Last but not least, the low popularity of active control is also caused by the lack of theoretical training among design engineers, as knowledge of both structural design and automatic control is required in this field.

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